

Uncertainty Principle for Kinetic Energy and Time?

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In quantum mechanics, there exist two well-known uncertainty principle statements, $(\Delta x)(\Delta p) \geq \hbar/2$ and $(\Delta E)(\Delta t) \geq \hbar/2$. The first is often obtained using the property $[-i\hbar d/dx, x] = -i\hbar$, where $-i\hbar d/dx$ is the momentum operator, but no such relation exists for the energy operator and time.

It is known that for a quantum bound system, even for a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls, the wavefunction $W(x)$ may be written in terms of all possible plane wave momentum states, $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, these states are taken to be physical. It is argued in this note that the form $\exp(ipx)$ is responsible for both the uncertainty in x and in t , or in other words the distributions of x and t . In the case of x , as one moves from x to $x+dx$, a shift occurs in the values of the two weights $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. Thus, it may appear as if one is 'losing' part of the quantum particle. Such behavior does not occur in classical physics. For a single $\exp(ipx)$, the modulus remains constant as one moves through space, but such is not the case for the average 'momentum state' $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$. In this case, there are losses and gains in space.

If one seems to 'lose' part of the average quantum particle as it moves from one point in space to another infinitesimally near, the same should occur as one moves through time. This leads to probability distributions in both time and space. Furthermore, there is a distribution in kinetic energy. For the Schrodinger equation, however, there is a single average E , even though some plane wave p kinetic energy values are greater than this value. Thus, it seems there is a spread in plane wave kinetic energy. A plane wave moves in space at constant v so $x=(p/m)t$. If one replaces $\exp(ipx)$ with this value, one obtains $\exp(i p^2 t/m)$ or $\exp(i 2 KE t)$. Thus, it seems that the p - x picture maps into a KE - t picture and so similar uncertainty relationships should exist for both. There is also a potential energy, however, which must be accounted for. In this note, we try to find an expression for the probability distribution in time and calculate the square root of the variance of t . In particular, we focus on the example of a particle in a box with an infinite potential. We also try to argue that including 'potential energy' in momentum space does not lead to an energy distribution and so write an uncertainty relationship for KE and t .

Classical Physics

In classical physics, it is sometimes argued that a density of $1/v(x)$ exists at each x , where v is the velocity at x . For a particle trapped in a box and bouncing back and forth after making elastic collisions with the walls, $v(x) = \text{constant}$, so there is no reason to expect a distribution of density in x or t . This leads to the question: Why should there be an x or t probability distribution in quantum mechanics?

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics seems to be based on the representation of a momentum state $\exp(ipx)$. Even for a wavefunction $W(x)$ in a potential, one may write a Fourier series $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$, where $\exp(ipx)$ is taken to be a physical momentum state. For other cases, such as the spatial density W^*W , the Fourier series does not

have such a physical meaning. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ describes two probability channels $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which are linked periodically. Thus, as one moves from x to $x+dx$, there is a shift in the values of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. For a single momentum state, the modulus $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ remains the same, but such is not the case for an average of momentum states, i.e. $W(x)$. As a result, $W^*(x)W(x)$ may show oscillatory humps, even for a particle trapped in a box. This is very different from classical physics. If one calculates an average of $\exp(ipx)$ states (i.e. the Fourier series of $W(x)$), each state, it seems, exists at a different time t . Thus, one might write a vector $(t_1, t_2, t_3 \dots)$ to describe the points in time for a particular average value $W(x)$ at spatial point x . As one moves to $x+dx$, the dt_i differ for each t_i because $dx = (p/m) dt_i$. Furthermore, an x distribution is created because $W(x)$ does not equal $W(x+dx)$, and W is real for all x in a bound state.

It seems one may argue there is also a time distribution. Thus, for a particular t , one might have the vector $(x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots)$ denoting different x points associated with a single t included in the t vector $(t_1, t_2, t, t_3 \dots)$. It seems this should lead to a distribution in time.

Consider a large number of identical quantum systems (or consider cycling). At a given time t , a particle may be in state p_1 at x_a in system 1, in state p_2 at x_b in system 2 etc. One may create an average across the systems based on $\exp(ipx)$ namely:

$\sum \over p_i \quad f_{p_i} \exp(i p_i x_a) / G(t)$. Here $G(t)$ is a normalization constant and p_i is a momentum which corresponds to x_a .

Next, one may ask what happens as time t changes to $t+dt$. In such a case, each x_a changes to $x_a + p_i dt$.

For the sake of argument, consider the case for which all x_a are 0, i.e. each quantum system happens to be at $x=0$ at time=0. Then, at a later time $t+dt$, one has:

$$\sum \over p \quad f_p \exp(i p^2 dt) = G(dt) \quad ((2))$$

The fact that $G(dt)$ is not the same as $G(t=0) = \sum \over p \quad f_p$ seems to show there is a time distribution which does not exist in a classical system. As time goes on, it seems dt becomes t because one only has different plane waves. The f_p 's are such that the following equation holds:

$$(\sum \over p \quad p^2/2m \quad f_p \exp(ipx)) / (\sum \over p \quad f_p \exp(ipx)) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

Thus, the role of the potential $V(x)$ seems to be to create fixed f_p weights for different plane waves, but one may think of quantum particle in a potential as an average of plane waves. The movement of these plane waves in time and space is known and so an average of plane waves is found to change in time and space.

Again, the reason for a distribution in t in the first place, seems to be the $\exp(ipx)$ nature of the momentum state. Motion in x space is similar to that in time for a plane wave and so if a distribution exists for x , it seems one should exist for t . Thus, the variance of t may be obtained using $G(t)^2$ as a time probability, it seems. One may

restrict the integral of t to a cycle, it seems, rather than necessarily integrating from $t=0$ to $t=\infty$.

From the Lorentz invariant quantity $x^2 - ct^2$, one may see that energy and time are linked. For a particle in a box, and even for plane wave states in a potential, a spread exists in p and so also in $p^2/2m$. Thus, one should be able to calculate (ΔKE) (Δt) directly, as one does for (Δx) (Δp) . In calculating the variance of $p^2/2m$, one may use:

$$\int dp \, KE^2 f_p^2 \quad (2)$$

We next try to apply these ideas to a particle in a box with infinite walls.

Quantum Particle in a Box with an Infinite Potential at the Walls

$W(x)$ for a particle with an infinite potential at the walls, say $x=-L/2$ and $x=L/2$. $W(x)=0$ at the walls is:

$$W(x) = \sqrt{2/L} \cos(k_{ave} x) \quad \text{where } k_{ave} = 3.14 n/L \quad \text{and } n \text{ odd} \quad (4)$$

This is obtained by solving the Schrodinger equation.

Inside the box, $\cos(k_{ave} x) = .5(\exp(i k_{ave} x) + \exp(-i k_{ave} x))$, and one might be tempted to consider the two addends as Fourier plane waves. If one calculates the Fourier transform, however, one has a rectangle function times $\cos(k_{ave} x)$ as $W(x)$ is 0 outside the range $-L/2 \leq x \leq L/2$. Thus, a Fourier transform, which may be found in the literature (1), exists for all p values. Interestingly, this result was presented in the 1990s.

For this problem, one may examine the uncertainty principle $(\Delta x)(\Delta p) \geq \frac{1}{2} \hbar$ (Here $\hbar = 1$)

In a handwavy manner, $\Delta x = L$ and momentum may be k_{ave} or $-k_{ave}$ so there exists a spread of $2k_{ave}$. Thus: $L (2) 3.14 n/L = 2(3.14)$ for $n=1$.

In keeping with this handwavy treatment, one may write $L = (p/m) \Delta t$ and so:

$$\Delta p = 2 k_{ave} L = 2 (p_{ave}^2/m) \Delta t$$

Thus, the $(\Delta x)(\Delta p)$ uncertainty relationship may be rewritten, albeit in a handwavy manner, in terms of average kinetic energy (which is total average Energy in this problem) and time.

One should also be able to solve for the uncertainty problem using $(\Delta x) = \sqrt{\text{Variance}(x)}$ and $(\Delta p) = \sqrt{\text{variance}(p)}$. For the (Δx) calculations one may use $P(x) = \text{probability} = W^2 = A^2 \cos^2 k_{ave} x$ where $k_{ave} = 3.14/L$ for the ground state. $A = \sqrt{2/L}$. f_p is given by (1):

$$f_p = \sqrt{L/3.14} (3.14n/(3.14n + kL)) \text{sinc}(.5(3.14n - kL)) \exp(i(n-1) 3.14/2) \quad (5)$$

In (1), exact values of the variances of x and p are given as:

$$\text{Var}(x) = L^2/12 \quad (1-6/(n^2 3.14^2)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Var}(p) = (n 3.14/L)^2$$

One may notice that after taking the square root of each variance and multiplying, the L factors cancel, leaving a number.

Next, one may consider kinetic energy and time variances. The kinetic energy variance in one dimension may be obtained through:

$$\text{Var}(KE) = \int dp \left(\frac{p^2}{2m} \right)^2 f(p)^2 - \left(\int dp \frac{p^2}{2m} f(p)^2 \right)^2 \quad ((6))$$

From ((5)) one sees that kL is present in $f(p)$ and that there is an overall \sqrt{L} . One uses $f(p)^2$ in the variance calculation in one dimension, so \sqrt{L} becomes L which may be combined with dp . Thus, one needs to multiply and divide by L^4 to accommodate the factor p^4 from KE squared. Thus, $\text{Var}(KE)$ goes as $1/kave^4$ and the square root of the variance as $1/kave^2$.

Next, $G(t)$ needs to be calculated from ((2)). For $f(p)$ from ((5)) it is known that:

$$\int dp f(p) \exp(ipx) = \sqrt{2/l} \cos(kave x) \quad ((7))$$

$f(p)$ is even in p and the integral ranges from minus infinite to plus infinite. Thus, it seems a contour integral may be performed to yield the RHS of ((7)). To calculate this, $\sin(.5(3.14n-kL))$ from the sinc function may be written as $(\exp(i \arg) - \exp(-i \arg)) / 2i$ and a semicircle in the positive i quadrants used for $\exp(i \arg)$ and in the negative for $\exp(-i \arg)$. A similar approach may be used for the calculation of $G(t)$, it seems.

$G(t) = \int dp f(p) \exp(i p^2 t)$ the integrand is also even and p ranges from minus infinite to plus infinite.

Thus, the same contour integral should apply with poles at $p=kave$ and $p=-kave$. Thus:

$$G(t) \text{ is proportional to } \cos(kave^2 t). \quad ((8))$$

A normalization constant, however, must be obtained using:

$$B^2 \int dt \cos^2(kave^2 t) = 1. \quad \text{This gives } B \text{ as proportional to } 1/L.$$

Thus, one may calculate the time variance from:

$$\text{Var}(t) = \int t^2 G(t)^2 dt - \left(\int t G(t)^2 dt \right)^2 \quad ((9))$$

It seems one may calculate this over a time cycle equivalent to the time taken to traverse the distance L and return i.e. $2L = (kave/m) t_{max}$.

((9)) should be proportional to $B^2 kave^6$ as one multiplies dt and t^2 by $kave^6$. Thus, $\text{Var}(t)$ is proportional to $kave^4$ and the square root of the variance to $kave^2$.

Multiplying $\sqrt{\text{Var}(t)}$ by $\sqrt{\text{Var}(KE)}$ yields a value proportional to L^2/L^2 .

Issue of a Potential

Given that the wavefunction $W(x)$ may be written as a Fourier series: $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$, all possible plane wave momentum states p enter into the picture, even those with kinetic energy greater than E , the average energy of the system. Thus, there is a spread in plane wave kinetic energy. This raises the question of the role of the potential energy. The bound state Schrodinger equation is given by:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V(x) W = E W \quad ((2))$$

If one writes both $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as separate Fourier series and collects terms with the same $\exp(ipx)$ one obtains:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} f_p + \sum_k V_k f_{(p-k)} = E f_p \quad ((3))$$

Thus, there exists a kind of conservation of energy equation for each momentum wave. If $\frac{p^2}{2m} \leq E$, then the second term on the LHS divided by f_p is $V(x)$ at the classical x point corresponding to p , otherwise the term is negative. Thus, to have a quantum bound state resonance, there is no spread in this 'type of total energy'. In other words, for each p , one has the same E . On the other hand, there is a spread of KE as a function of p . Thus, perhaps one should think of an uncertainty relationship in terms of kinetic energy and time. As noted, it is as if the role of the potential is to create the f_p weights of the $\exp(ipx)$ plane waves. An average of these plane waves then accounts for the correct kinetic energy $(\sum_p f_p \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx)) / (\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx))$.

Conclusion

In this note, we have tried to examine a reason for the existence of both uncertainty relationships for x and p and E or KE and t . We argue that the behavior of $\exp(ipx)$ is responsible for the probability distributions for both x and t . For a single momentum state, a change in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ occurs as one moves from x to $x+dx$, but the modulus remains unchanged. Such is not the case for an average i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$. Then, one obtains an average complex number (or real for a bound state) with a modulus which changes from x to $x+dx$. Since a particle moves in both space and time, we argue this affect also creates a distribution in time. We try to estimate a 'wavefunction' for the time distribution as $G(t) = \sum_p f_p \exp(i \frac{p^2}{2m} t)$ and investigate the case of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls. In such a case, a factor of L^2 from the variance of time cancels $1/L^2$ from the variance of $\frac{p^2}{2m}$, where L is the length of the box. This is in keeping with handwavy treatments for which one uses the entire KE as the possible uncertainty in energy. We also argue that there is a spread in kinetic energy even for a potential and perhaps this should be used in the uncertainty relationship.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box